

Core Competencies Required in Commercial Grain Farming: A Scoping Review

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The study conducted recently investigating the impact of entrepreneurship on food security among smallholder farmers indicated low levels of entrepreneurship and high levels of food insecurity among the farmers. Therefore, this scoping review aimed to map the existing literature on the core competencies required in commercial grain farming to transfer such to the future aspirant farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa. There were 8 articles which met the inclusion criteria. From the selected studies, half of the studies ($n=4$) used quantitative methods and qualitative research approach. Majority of the studies ($n=6$) were conducted in South Africa while one ($n=1$) study was conducted in Nigeria and another ($n=1$) in Kenya, Nigeria and Uganda. Findings indicated that for one to be involved into commercial farming should possess certain competencies and these competencies are shared in Sub-Saharan African countries. For instance, this research indicated that educational skills in terms of basic literacy are seen as high skills needed in South Africa. Again, in South Africa the farmers' personal attributes matter as they should encompass the managerial and leadership skills needed for commercial farming, on the one hand. On the other hand, in Nigeria, it indicated that the core competency in commercial families should include technical skills. Furthermore, implications for future research are also made as well as practical implications on policy and general management of the farm.

Keywords: Scoping review, grain farming, commercial farming, competency

The nature of skills identifiable from farmers who present entrepreneurial orientation include (1) business and management skills such as accountancy, financial capability, strategic planning and people management, (2) co-operation and networking skills, (3) information technology skills, (4) marketing and selling skills, (5) entrepreneurial quality and values and (6) technical and professional skill such as exact farming skills (McElwee & Robson, 2005). Hill (2007) in Phelan (2014) generated set of skills ranging from business planning, financial management, people management, sales and marketing, collaboration, to leadership and risk management. Though the list outlines skills that are generally entrepreneurial in nature, they may also be described as business and management skills and competencies (Phelan, 2014).

Competency and/or competence cannot be used interchangeably. "Competence is a combination of the complex attributes of knowledge, skills, and attitudes; with the ability to make professional judgement and to perform intelligently in specific situations" (Leung et al., 2016, pp. 189-190).

Competency is described as an underlying characteristic of performance; it is multifaceted and difficult to measure. Broadly speaking, competence reflects a person's cognitive approach to a task, encompassing the multiple attributes of knowledge, skills and attitudes, whereas competency highlights a person's ability to perform those tasks within the defined

context of professional practice (p. 190).

According to Schippmann (2010, p. 198), competencies refer to "measurable, organizationally relevant, and behaviourally based capabilities of people." McLagan defines competency as "an area of knowledge or skill that is critical for producing key outputs" (Grobler et al., 2011, p. 560). Competency includes "a broad range of knowledge, skills, traits and behaviours that may be technical in nature (e.g., being a good computer programmer), relate to interpersonal skills (e.g., having good communication skills) or be business-orientated (e.g., being a good financial advisor)" (Van Aswegen, 2012, p. 135). According to Spencer and Spencer, it is "an underlying characteristic of an individual that is causally related to criterion-referenced effective and/or superior performance in a job or situation." Similarly, DuBois views it as "an underlying characteristic that leads to successful performance in life" (Grobler et al., 2011, p. 561). Pulakos (2009) adds that knowledge, skills, abilities and other personal characteristics are most instrumental for achieving important job outcomes and contribute to organisational success.

A Cambodian study examined the core competencies among the agricultural development professionals famously known as extension workers. The survey used in that study consisted of 48 competencies representing eight core competencies; each competency had a level of importance and competency parts. The findings showed that extension workers in Cambodia deemed all competencies highly or very highly important to their extension work. Conversely, these extension workers' perceived level of competency in those competencies appeared not to meet the expectations. Their level of competency in all, but communication skills and diversity significantly differed by gender, but not by age and experience. The study further found 148 four methods of acquiring core competencies (pre-service, in-service, basic induction training, & participation in seminars, workshops, & webinars) as appropriate (Suvedi et al., 2018).

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This study adopts the view held by Spencer and Spencer, and DuBois because this one is much more inclusive of knowledge or skill and any number of other characteristics, such as the level of motivation and personality traits.

The discussion on farmer competencies kicks off with the study from the Dutch dairy farmers which explored the craft, managerial and entrepreneurial competencies in relation to psychological variables and venture success (Bergevoet, 2005). Using craft, managerial, entrepreneurial, opportunity, strategic, conceptual, organising and relationship competencies as well as skills, Bergevoet found a positive relationship between higher scores in these competencies and entrepreneurial venture success. In a subsequent study, Bergevoet and Van Woerkum (2006) found that entrepreneurial competencies can be enhanced using farmer led study groups.

Furthermore, commercial farms within the American context refer to farms that generate annual gross sales of \$40 000 or more (Kraenzle et al., 1989). Commercial farming refers mainly to "increased participation in remunerative agricultural commercial output markets" (Khapayi & Celliers, 2016, p. 26). For example, in the livestock sector, commercial farming aims "to achieve faster growth, less mortality, high turnover which all translate into higher profits" (Masika et al., 1998, p. 34) the same could be assumed for grain farming. Farm sizes also form a distinguishing criterion between smallholder farmers and commercial farmers (Cousins, 2009). Hall (2009, p. 51) "indicates that a higher degree of labour-intensity distinguishes smallholders from commercial farmers, and sometimes smallholding appears to be equated with farming that relies mainly on household labour." Therefore, the definition adopted in this study considers the features mentioned above. Measures to make commercial and subsistence smallholder farming more productive and sustainable, as proposed by the World Bank (2007) include: improve price incentives and increase the quality and quantity of public investment; make product markets work better; improve access to financial services and reduce risks; enhance the performance of producer organisations; promote innovation through science and technology (Baiphethi & Jacobs, 2009).

Problem Statement

The study conducted recently in South Africa investigating the impact of entrepreneurship on food security among smallholder farmers indicated low levels of entrepreneurship and high levels of food insecurity among the farmers (Sinyolo & Mudhara, 2018). Upon realisation that the debate on farm entrepreneurial competency is still at an infancy stage, Moloi (2021) contributed to research by developing a competency model for commercial grain farmers as this study sought to respond to the National Development Plan Vision 2030, South Africa's blueprint whose aim is to increase the number of commercial farmers primarily from the previously marginalised communities. Focusing on the role of a commercial grain farmer is made because these farmers are projected as employment creators in the National Development Plan Vision 2030 (NDP Vision 2030, 2012).

Therefore, the purpose of this scoping review is to identify the competencies of a commercial grain farmer. Beyond the South African borders, there may be some competencies relevant that could be learned especially from the Sub-Saharan Africa.

Review Question

What are the core competencies required in commercial grain

farmers that can be transferred to future aspirant farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa?

Aim of the Study

This scoping review was to map the existing literature on the core competencies required in commercial grain farmers to transfer such to the future aspirant farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Objectives of the Study

- To identify the core competencies required in commercial grain farming in Sub-Saharan Africa.
- To recommend the core competencies required in commercial grain farming for transfer to the future aspirant farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Method

A scoping review was adopted to map the existing literature on the core competencies needed for commercial farming. This scoping review is a relatively new approach for which there is not yet a universal study definition or definitive procedure (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005). It is an approach to reviewing the literature which to date has received little attention in the research methods literature (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005). Arksey and O'Malley's (2005) six step approach due to its ability to explore broader topics by mapping the existing literature (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005) and making recommendations for future studies. To start off, the researchers identified the research question as "*What are the core competencies required in commercial grain farming that can be transferred to future farmers from previously marginalised communities in South Africa?*"

Local (African Journal & Science Direct) and international databases (EBSCOhost & PubMed) were used to searching for relevant data while also incorporating the professional service of Ms. AI Khangale, the faculty librarian as Arksey and O'Malley (2005) recommends teamwork with professional help. The researchers used Boolean operators, truncations, and MeSH terms to search for relevant studies. To accumulate more literature, research rabbit tool was used and backward and forward was done on Google Scholar. The preliminary developed search strategy is as follow: "competency" OR "skill" OR "knowledge" AND "commercial" AND "grain" AND "farming" OR "agriculture".

Two reviewers (TJ & MM) were responsible for identifying relevant articles. On this step, Arksey and O'Malley (2005) stated that researchers must develop inclusion and exclusion criteria. The researcher used SPIDER framework to develop the inclusion criteria. In terms of sample, the study included studies which focused on studies that were conducted with farmers aged 18 years and older because many farmers choose not to go on retirement. The phenomenon of interest were core competencies skills and knowledge. As for the design, the researchers included studies which were conducted using qualitative, quantitative and mixed method approaches within the period of 2014 - 2024 to ensure that the review reflects recent or current dynamics around the phenomenon at hand.

The articles which met the inclusion criteria were charted on the developed data chart (see table 1) and two reviewers were involved in this process (TJ & MM). After charting the data, two more reviewers were responsible for indicating which areas should be prioritised when collecting data (Arksey & O'Malley, 2005). Thus,

we provided a descriptive analysis of approaches, setting/context, and population and provide a content synthesis on the main findings. Two reviewers, TJ and MM were responsible for synthesising data

with TS serving as a mediator and resolving conflicts.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criterion

Criteria	Include or exclude	Include or exclude? Provide brief justification
Full text journal studies	Include	We believe that the studies went through a rigorous review process.
Peer reviewed studies	Include	We believe that the studies went through a rigorous review process.
Non-peer reviewed studies	Exclude	We believe that the studies did not go through a rigorous review.
Quantitative studies	Include	We believe that the studies went through a rigorous review process.
Qualitative studies	Include	We believe that the studies went through a rigorous review process.
Mixed method studies	Include	We believe that the studies went through a rigorous review process.
Review studies	Exclude	We cannot review the review as we are not conducting meta-analysis.
PhD theses/ Masters' dissertations/mini-dissertations	Include	The researcher will include PhD theses and dissertations and go through rigorous review processes of ethical clearance. If the study is unethical, the researcher will not be allowed to proceed with the study.
Conference proceedings	Exclude	We believe that the presented papers might not have gone through a rigorous review.
Studies published in languages other than English and/or Afrikaans	Exclude	The researcher can comprehend English, and studies written in other languages were excluded.

Characteristics of the Included Studies

The data chart above indicates that there were 8 articles which met the inclusion criteria. From the selected studies, half of the studies ($n= 4$) used quantitative methods (Balogun et al., 2021; Khapayi & Celliers, 2016; Musekenyi et al., 2023; Xaba & Urban, 2016) and qualitative research approach (Mafukata, 2015; Volschenk, 2022). Majority of the studies ($n= 6$) were conducted in South Africa (Balogun et al., 2021; Khapayi & Celliers, 2016; Mafukata, 2015; Volschenk, 2022; Xaba, 2014; Xaba & Urban, 2016) with one ($n= 1$) study being conducted in Nigeria (Balogun et al., 2021) and another ($n= 1$) conducted in Kenya, Nigeria and Uganda (Adeyanju et al., 2023).

Main Findings: Core Competencies Needed

The sampled data indicated that for one to be involved into commercial farming should possess certain competencies and these competencies are shared in Sub-Saharan African countries. For instance, Mafukata (2015) and Volschenk (2022) indicated that educational skills in terms of basic literacy are seen as high skills needed in South Africa. Moreover, some scholars such as Volschenk (2022) and Khapayi and Celliers (2016) found that educational knowledge should not just be basic but should also include digital knowledge in South Africa. Again, in South Africa the farmers' personal attributes matter as they should encompass the managerial and leadership skills needed for commercial farming (Mafukata, 2015; Volschenk, 2022). On the other hand, in Nigeria, Balogun et al. (2021) indicated that the core competency in commercial families should include technical skills. The technical skills include conservation of agricultural practices, knowledge of the season, quantity of seed planted, farm size and amount of man-day labour used (Balogun et al., 2021; Xaba, 2014).

Discussion

Three themes have been developed for this scoping review and are discussed below under level of education, personal attributes and technical skill.

Level of Education

The need to determine the level of education is espoused by the findings as core competencies required by commercial farmers. For example, Terblanché (2006) investigated the need for a new generation of farmers in South Africa. "According to the Strategic Plan for South African Agriculture, it recognises the importance of the youth, emphasises the education and training of the youth, to ensure a new generation of farmers and agriculturists" (Terblanché, 2006, p. 132). This assertion is further corroborated by Díaz-Pichardo et al. (2012, p. 91) who stated, "Developing entrepreneurial competency in the agricultural sector means bringing the farmer from the 'farmer as farmer' position to the 'farmer as entrepreneur' level through an educational process."

Moreover, acquiring digital knowledge is consistent with Moloji (2021)'s findings on the need for farmers to be technologically savvy or working smart. McLean-Meynsse and Brown (1994) also found that early adoption of new technology leads to farming success while Ghadiyali et al. (2011) further added that farmers get a low price for their yield for reasons such as lack of price information and lack of technological knowledge.

Generally, adequate literacy level helps improve farmers in the management of their enterprises in terms of decision making, understanding of the financial statements as well as human resource management. Market information is also better understood when the level of education is at an advanced level which further incorporates the use of digital tools.

Personal Attributes

For farmers to have relevant personal attributes are further supported by Alstete (2008) who indicated that other leading personality themes that seem to predict entrepreneurial success are the commitment and determination of entrepreneurs, their leadership and the ability to build teams, drive for finding opportunities, tolerance for risk, creativity, self-reliance, and general enthusiasm to do exceptionally well. Similarly, this leadership skill is mainly captured in Man et al. (2002) organising competency which is

related to the organisation of different internal and external human, physical, financial and technological resources, including team building, leading employees, training and controlling. Moloi (2021) also confirmed that having personality attributes serve as core competencies where farmers need to exhibit mainly passion, work dedication, self-efficacy, humbleness/aggressiveness, intelligence, emotional stability and patience.

In a nutshell, these personal attributes are considered paramount especially for farmers because Moloi (2021) predicted in his competency model that those attributes contribute to farm success. Additionally, Man et al. (2002) attested to the fact that commitment competencies focus on competencies that drive the entrepreneur to move ahead with the business.

Technical Skill

Technical skill also has sufficient support from literature. Though Nuthall (2006) classified having technical knowledge and skill as core for experts, this skill appears as production skill in Moloi (2021) study and entails a broad range of other related skills such as ploughing, planting, cultivating, spraying for diseases and harvesting. Man et al. (2002) categorised this skill as conceptual competency as it focuses on competencies related to different conceptual abilities, which are reflected in the behaviours of the entrepreneur (e.g., decision skills, absorbing & understanding complex information, risk-taking & innovativeness).

Regarding the objectives of this scoping review, the first one sought to identify the core competencies required in commercial farming in Sub-Saharan Africa. As shown in the discussion above, competencies such as educational level, personal attributes and technical skill were identified and fully explained accordingly. Identification of these skills not only does it help researchers and trainers to design the training material, but it also further assists career counsellors and psychologists match future aspirant farmers with the relevant personal attributes. Additionally, training and educational institutions stand a chance of aligning their training programmes with up-to-date scientifically informed developments. Gains attributable to human resource professionals, especially job analysts would be ability to update job descriptions and structure compensation packages accordingly for the workforce in this sector.

The second objective sought to recommend the core competencies required in commercial farming for transfer to the future aspirant farmers in Sub-Saharan Africa. Thus, as per Khapayi and Celliers (2016) findings on insufficient land availability to expand production by emerging farmers, the land issue is still exacerbated by government's slow transfer to the deserving group that is in majority in South Africa. Moloi (2021) contradictory finding indicated that land ownership is not a hurdle on competency acquisition. Be that as it may, the previously marginalised community continue to remain landless even after thirty years into South Africa's democracy.

Conclusion

There is still paucity of research around farming competency in all farming types, namely, crop, livestock and in mixed farming especially in sub-Saharan Africa. It thus appears that new future studies would expand our knowledge if they would adopt the mixed methods approach which is lagging far behind as shown in this scoping review. There may be some studies on crop farming but with grain so much still needs to be done.

Limitations of this Study

One of the major limitations of this study is that language played a huge role in excluding studies that were not reported in English within the sub-Saharan Africa as the researcher could only understand it. Another limitation is that this scoping review excluded all other reviews as the interest lied on reports on primary data only. Conference proceedings were also excluded with the belief that they might not have gone through a rigorous peer review process. Similarly, non-peer review studies were excluded for the same reason.

Practical Implications of this Research

On the entrepreneurship level, managing a farm generally requires advanced entrepreneurial skill in terms of leadership, financial management as well as human capital management which is mainly a serious challenge in this sector. These competencies would assist managers to design appropriate job descriptions that could even save employers from litigation by employees for not knowing what their job entails.

Recommendations for Future Research

The researcher therefore suggests the following recommendations:

- Future research may consider expanding farming competency mainly in crops as they are the primary source of food for both humans and animals.
- Future research may further consider adopting mixed method approaches as few studies have been done.
- Future research may further focus on female farmers regarding acquisition of farming competencies. Though their presence may be felt on smallholder front, this is not yet evident on commercial level.
- Future research may further focus on determining competency relationship between male and female farmers.

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